

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2023 Annual Report

Volume 3

Annual Program Progress

Coordination, Data Management, and Communication

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Researchers and Partners (i.e., Agency Staff and Conservation Professionals) work in small groups to assess effectiveness of current Monitoring Program Communication tools at the 2024 Annual Workshop, January 10, 2024.

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Contents

Field and Lab Coordination.....	5
1) By The Numbers	6
2) Protocols and Metadata Collection	12
Data Management Infrastructure.....	12
3) Overview.....	13
4) Electronic Data Collection Surveys	14
5) Pilot Data Dashboard.....	15
6) Standardized Data Upload.....	15
7) Quality Assurance & Quality Control.....	15
8) Semi-automated Data Summaries.....	16
Research Communication and Collaboration	16
9) 2023 Workshop	17
10) Scientific Conferences and Working Groups	17
11) Leveraged Funds to Strengthen Monitoring Capacity.....	18
Public Communication and Outreach	19
12) 2023 Webinar and Brochure.....	19
13) Public Presentations and Outreach Events	19

Note: The data and management summaries contained in this report are provisional. Every effort has been made to ensure their correctness. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is supported by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the US Environmental Protection Agency's Great Lake Restoration Initiative, and the Ohio Water Development Authority. The information, findings, and conclusions in this article are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the funding organizations. Any use of trade, product, or firm names is for descriptive purposes only and does not imply endorsement by the State of Ohio or U.S. Government. Contact the ODNR'S H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program prior to using these data and before citing research and management findings.

Field and Lab Coordination

By The Numbers

In 2023, Monitoring Program field crews had > 260 field visits across ~ 50 H2Ohio wetland projects (Table 1.1). Geographic base crews collected > 1800 surface water samples and > 700 soil samples (Table 1.2). Of the total 267 field visits in 2023, approximately 80 field visits were for specialty crew data collection, including drone flights and image processing (Table 1.3), sensor network deployments (Table 1.4), subsurface soil hydrogeophysical parameters (Table 1.5), and 3-D hydrodynamic model development and calibration (Table 1.6). Program researchers drafted or updated 26 Project Specific Routine Monitoring Plans (see details below *Protocols and Metadata Collection*).

Table 1.1. Total field visits across Wetland Projects for each quarter in 2023.

Field Visit Type	December 2022 - February 2023		March - May 2023		June - August 2023		September - December 2023		Total	
	Visits	Projects	Visits	Projects	Visits	Projects	Visits	Projects	Visits	Projects
Routine Monitoring	37	13	69	25	112	26	69	19	175	26
Site Characterization or Training	24	14	41	22	68	24	27	17	92	25
Total	61	27	110	57	180	50	96	36	267	51

Table 1.2. Summary of water and soil samples collected by Base Crews in 2023, and the proportion of collected samples that have been analyzed for nutrient content in 2023. Bolded rows indicate Focal Projects.

Base Crew	Project Code	Project Name	Routine Monitoring	Samples		% Analyzed	
				Water	Soil	Water	Soil
Northwest Inland	FORB	17. Forder Bridge	●	154	80	77	64
	MAUR	31. Maumee River Floodplain	●	12	14	100	100
	MONW	6. Montpelier Wetland		0	11	–	0
	OOPR	13. Oak Openings Preserve	●	41	24	88	100
	OAKE	21. Oakwoods East	●	52	92	92	47
	OAKW	20. Oakwoods West	●	48	66	100	52
	OTSS	50. Otsego Schools		25	19	72	74
	SJCO	10. St. Joseph Confluence	●	13	21	100	100
	SJRE	11. St. Joseph's River Restoration	●	121	53	93	0
	VANO	25. Van Order	●	17	15	100	100
WEIP	33. Weisgerber-Pohlman	●	11	14	100	100	
Northcentral	ANDW	23. Andreoff Wetland	●	6	0	100	–
	BLAR	19. Blanchard River	●	10	0	100	–
	BUEF	32. Buehler Farms	●	7	3	100	0
	CBMC	37. Clary-Boulee-McDonald		19	9	100	0
	FRUW	22. Fruth Wetland	●	18	12	100	0
	REDB	16. Redhorse Bend	●	185	34	86	62
	SRHE	24. Sandusky River Headwaters	●	36	7	100	0
	SUGB	47. Sugarcamp 7	●	16	3	100	0
UPPB	46. Upper Blanchard	●	12	6	100	0	
Northeast	BIRB	41. Bird Bog		2	0	0	–
	CHIL	62. Chippewa Lake		7	6	29	100
	FOSR	43. Fosters Run		4	0	75	–
	FUNB	69. Funk Bottoms		3	0	0	–
	HEAD	42. Headlands Dunes		5	0	80	–
	MARR	40. Martin's Run		6	0	0	–
	TRUC	49. Trumbull Creek	●	16	48	31	0
Northwest Coastal	BOHM	58. Bohling Marsh	●	4	0	100	–
	DARR	59. Darby Refuge	●	61	6	85	67

Base Crew	Project Code	Project Name	Routine Monitoring	Samples		% Analyzed	
				Water	Soil	Water	Soil
Northwest Coastal	DUCO	36. Duck and Otter		25	0	0	–
	MAGM	5. Magee Marsh	●	169	50	54	6
	NORR	14. North Ridge	●	75	12	73	25
	OTTN	4. Ottawa NWR	●	41	6	83	33
Southwest & Central	BAUD	27. Baughman Ditch		0	3	–	0
	BDCR	98. Big Darby Creek		1	2	100	0
	BROP	61. Brooks Park	●	167	22	87	0
	BWLK	60. Burntwood-Langenkamp	●	243	26	88	0
	COLW	105. Coldwater Wetland		0	5	–	0
	COOC	97. Cooks Creek		4	6	100	0
	GORF	79. Gorman Farm		4	3	100	0
	MERW	67. Mercer Wetland		54	4	85	0
	ODOW	66. O'Donnell Wetland		4	4	100	0
	PERC	96. Perfect Creek		4	0	100	–
	SPRC	64. Springcreek Confluence	●	88	6	94	0
	SPRR	76. Spring Run		6	15	83	0
	TIPC	65. Tipp City	●	60	3	92	0
	WALC	71. Walnut Creek		30	4	100	0
			Total	1886	714		

Table 1.3. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Drone Imagery collection, processing, and application toward Vegetation Classification in 2023. For additional details about monitoring at these Projects, see Vol. 1 of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2023 Annual Report. For a key connecting four-letter Project code to full Project name, see Table 1.2.

Task	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Drone Flight				MAUB, SJRE	TRUC, BWLK	MAGM	SJRE, OAKE, OAKW, FORB, BWLK	REDB, FORB, BROP, MAGM				
Image Processing	FORB	MAGM, 2022 QC	MAGM, 2022 QC	MAGM	TRUC	OAKE, OAKW		BWLK, OAKW, OAKE	REDB, MAGM	BROP, TRUC	OAKW, OAKE	FORB
Vegetation Classification	FORB			FORB	MAGM			OAKW			MAGM	

Table 1.4. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Sensor Network parameters, Projects, and deployment locations for sensor installation that occurred in 2022 and 2023. MAGM = Magee Marsh Coastal Reconnection Project and SJRE = St. Joseph’s River Restoration Project. An “x” indicates a sensor for given parameter was deployed at the respective location in a Project. Within the sensor network, each Project features several strategically placed devices that continuously track soil, water, and atmospheric parameters every ten minutes. For additional details about monitoring at these two Projects, see Vol. 1 of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2023 Annual Report.

		MAGM					SJRE			
Parameter	Units	Base	WCS 1	Downstr.	WCS 2	Upstr.	Base	Wells	North Src.	Pools
Meteorology	Air Temperature	°C	x				x			
	Air Pressure at Sea Level	mb	x				x			
	Dewpoint Temperature	°C	x				x			
	Photosynthetic Active Radiation	µmol/m ² /s ¹	x				x			
	Precipitation Accumulation	mm	x				x			
	Relative Humidity	%	x				x			
	Wind Direction	degrees	x				x			
	Wind Gust	m/s	x				x			
	Wind Speed	m/s	x				x			
	Hydrology	Water Height in Stream	mm						x	
Specific Conductance		µS/cm		x	x	x		x		
Water Temperature		°C		x	x	x		x		
Depth of water		mm		x	x		x		x	x
Distance to water		mm		x	x		x		x	x
Turbidity	FNU		x	x	x					
Soil	Soil Conductivity	farad/m						x		
	Soil Temperature	°C						x		
	Soil Volumetric Water Content	%						x		

Table 1.5. Hydrogeophysics data collection in 2023. GPR = Ground penetrating radar transects, EC = soil electrical conductivity transects, ERT = electrical resistivity tomography transects, SOIL = discrete soil samples, PIEZ = groundwater monitoring well installation, BATH = bathymetry, INFIL = infiltration tests. For additional details about monitoring at these Projects, see Vol. 1 of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring 2023 Program Annual Report. For a key connecting four-letter Project code to full Project name see Table 1.2.

Data	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
GPR			BWLK	BWLK					OAKE, OAKW	
EC							BWLK, OAKE, OAKW			
ERT					BWLK	BWLK			OAKE, OAKW	
SOIL	BROP							BWLK		
PIEZ	BROP	SJRE		SJRE, BROP				BWLK	OAKE, OAKW	
BATH						MAGM				
INFIL										OAKE, OAKW

Table 1.6. Three-dimensional (3D) Hydrodynamic Model Development and Calibration Progress in 2023. For additional details about monitoring at these Projects, see Vol 1 of the 2024 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Annual Report. For a key connecting four-letter Project code to full Project name see Table 1.2.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Model Development								OAKE, OAKW			FORB	
Model Calibration								BROP, SJRE	<i>(Pending data)</i>			

Protocols and Metadata Collection

November 8 Workshop

Researchers met in person for a workshop on November 8, 2023, to draft protocols for the monitoring program. The group outlined protocol needs and plans for completion of over 40 protocols that require compilation and refinement.

Project Specific Monitoring Plans

Project Specific Monitoring Plans were refined for the 26 Projects in Routine Monitoring in 2023. In addition, crews compiled and overlaid USDA soil maps, Project Design Plans, Wetland Features and Flow Paths via a [wetland characterization mapping workflow](#).

Project Characterization and Attribute Compilation

A workflow for [project characterization and attribute compilation](#) was created in 2023, which establishes the framework for information collection related to “onboarding” new H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Projects.

Data Management Infrastructure

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program collects a variety of data types through a range of methods in Projects throughout Ohio. The Monitoring Program’s diffuse and diverse data collection requires diligent management that supports centralization and assures quality. The development of data management workflows for the Monitoring Program was primarily performed by the Chief Data Manager and the Wetland Data Specialist, with several contributions from the Research Coordinator and Monitoring Program staff. A portion of this work was supported by additional funding for Sensor Network expansion from the Great Lakes Restoration Initiative (see details below *Leveraged Funds to Strengthen Monitoring Capacity*).

In 2023, several workflows were improved and implemented to verify data quality and improve efficiency of data collection and distribution for Base and Specialty Crews. The workflows described in more detail below were drafted and user-tested in 2021–2022 with many successfully launched and improved in 2023. In general, data management highlights include:

- Updated electronic data collection surveys used to standardize and centralize data entry: four surveys refined and one new survey developed for internal Monitoring Program use, and three data collection and management tracking surveys finalized for external partner use in 2023. See details below **Electronic Data Collection Surveys**.
- Developed a Pilot Data Dashboard and shared with Ohio Department of Natural Resources managers and select external partners in 2023. See details below **Pilot Data Dashboard**.
- Developed automated workflows to transfer sensor-collected data daily to version-controlled repositories on the hosting service GitHub and assess data quality.

- Developed a centralized and semi-automated workflow for recurrent upload of analytical chemistry and field data by Base and Specialty Crews in standardized formats to the hosting service GitHub.
- Developed program-wide quality control tests and acceptance criteria for tabular data in 2023, to be fully implemented and automated in 2024.
- Developed semi-automated system to generate data summaries and relevant maps for each Wetland Project with substantive data collected to date.

Overview

Figure 3.1. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Data Management Plan Overview.

Data Management is a critical component of the Monitoring Program given it supports robust data collection, guarantees data reliability, facilitates the integration of diverse dataset types, and ensures long-term data access. The broad spatial and temporal extent of the Monitoring Program, along with the diversity of data types collected by Base and Specialty Crews, reinforces the importance of developing a robust Data Management Plan, and highlights the complexity warranted by such a comprehensive system. Tools and workflows have been designed, tested, and implemented throughout 2021–2023 to address some major stages of the data lifecycle, including data generation by sensors and Monitoring Program personnel, data collection via custom-built tools, data harvesting into cloud-based data repositories, data quality assessments via automated processes, and near-term and long-term data storage solutions. One major accomplishment of the Data Management Plan designed and implemented to date is the standardization and centralization of all manual field data collected by distributed crews across the state via custom-built digital forms, which produces consistent datasets that are all stored in one common repository. Other Monitoring Program-wide criteria have also been developed to ensure that the quality of datasets is consistent throughout the Program and is clearly described

to internal and external data users to corroborate the degree to which data are known to be accurate.

Several automated workflows that employ programming-based tools (i.e., computer code) have been developed to effectively implement the Data Management Plan, enforce Monitoring Program-wide criteria, and accelerate the steps of processing and integrating datasets to ultimately generate useful data products. Steps that involve data quality assessment have been iteratively developed and automated to efficiently check if datasets meet the minimum acceptance criteria to be used in further analysis that inform decision making. Other useful automated workflows include the generation of data summary reports that provide basic statistical tables, graphs, and maps of relevant data to Monitoring Program personnel to foster the identification and practical interpretation of preliminary data patterns. Fully revised versions of the summary reports are publicly released in this Annual Report. The Data Management Plan is iteratively developed, gradually implemented, and frequently revised to advance along with the Monitoring Program's data needs.

Electronic Data Collection Surveys

Electronic data collection forms (hereafter “surveys”) developed for several data streams in 2022 using Esri ArcGIS Survey123 (e.g., water and soil sample metadata, physicochemical measurements, vegetation community composition and biomass sample metadata, and sensor status tracking) were iterated and considerably refined in 2023. These surveys are custom-built data entry systems that support specific data types and data collection needs of each Crew. Surveys achieve four programmatic data management goals:

1. Ensure thorough metadata documentation and unique sample identification and tracking.
2. Implement comprehensive quality assurance steps to reduce errors.
3. Increase efficiency by removing data transcription (in lieu of only analog data records).
4. Seamlessly centralize data storage from all Crews into one common repository.

In 2023, four surveys were considerably refined, and one new survey was released for internal use. The refined surveys are used by Base and Specialty Crews in 1) Routine Monitoring of completed Wetland Projects, 2) Site characterization and supplemental sampling at Wetland Projects in pre- or post-construction, 3) Logging of sensor status (e.g., deployment, calibration), and 4) Vegetation community composition and biomass sampling. To date, over 95% of water, soil, and biomass samples and physicochemical measurements collected by Monitoring Program staff have been recorded via the surveys available for internal use. The newly built survey was developed for the Vegetation and Drone Specialty Crews to support the delineation of vegetation patches using spatial accuracy compatible with drone imagery. The high-accuracy patch delineations are used in downstream analysis in a novel machine-learning workflow.

The three publicly available surveys developed and tested in 2022 were further refined and released in 2023 to support the Monitoring Program’s collaborative efforts. The “Site

Characterization and Supplemental Sampling” survey allows external partners collecting samples at Wetland Projects to use identical workflows to the ones employed internally, which substantially improves data integration. The “Coastal Management Tracking” and “Management Actions Tracking” surveys track water level, vegetation, and other types of management actions in coastal and non-coastal Wetland Projects, respectively. In 2023, the public surveys were more broadly shared with respective partners and continue to be stress-tested with user expansion. The Monitoring Program’s primary objective for the publicly available surveys is to facilitate aggregation of all H2Ohio-related datasets by centralizing data collected at Wetland Projects, facilitating data access, and sharing and employing consistent data quality criteria across Projects.

Pilot Data Dashboard

A provisional Data Dashboard was developed in 2023 using ArcGIS Experience. The Dashboard contains two main sections composed of Wetland Project sample metadata and attributes, and real-time meteorologic and water quality sensor data. The Wetland Project attributes section contains provisional (raw) sample metadata and physicochemical measurements collected using the electronic surveys, along with information about deployed sensors, staff gauges, Chronologs, and groundwater wells at individual Wetland Projects. The real-time sensor section contains a live feed of select sensor variables for Wetland Projects that have sensor networks. In future iterations, the Data Dashboard will also contain quality-checked nutrient content data for water and soil samples.

Standardized Data Upload

A standardized system for data uploads by Base and Specialty Crews was developed in 2023 to increase the efficiency, centralization, and internal access to datasets. Nutrient content, deployable sensors, and nutrient flux data are included in templates and periodically uploaded to the online repository GitHub. In future iterations, data uploads will trigger downstream workflows that log upload attributes (e.g., number of files, type of data), and data-specific quality control workflows (e.g., specific acceptance criteria).

Quality Assurance & Quality Control

Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) are critical components of the Monitoring Program data management infrastructure. These processes vary from near real-time to manual assessments, tailored to the unique data needs of each sensor, dataset, and collection method within the Program. These QA/QC processes serve to minimize errors and validate data quality to ensure it meets the standards necessary for impactful data analysis and evidence-based decision making. The QA/QC workflows for the Monitoring Program operate under a program-wide framework, which is iteratively under development and has been outlined in the Quality Assurance Project Plan (QAPP) developed for Sensor Network expansion with funding from the

Great Lakes Restoration Initiative (see details below *Leveraged Funds to Strengthen Monitoring Capacity*).

Central to the QA/QC processes are a host of task-specific, Python-based tools, designed to execute various quality control tests. These tools automate quality checks through continuous integration systems like GitHub Actions. The structure of these processes follows standard methodology that includes assessing each data point against established criteria, flagging data based on test outcomes, and systematically documenting quality issues and resolutions. This programmatic and automated data management approach allows for the design of efficient, replicable, and scalable systems geared toward near-real-time data handling that is consistent and reliable. Moreover, a standardized quality flag system developed for the Monitoring Program will guide data users in assessing a dataset's quality and reinforce the data's reliability for downstream analyses.

Semi-automated Data Summaries

A semi-automated system was developed in 2023 to generate standardized data summaries for each Wetland Project with substantive data collected to date. The data summaries contain basic statistics in tables, relevant maps, and figures, along with relevant interpretation provided by each individual Base and Specialty Crew for hydrology, nutrient content of water, soil, and biomass samples, and vegetation community composition. In future implementations, the data summaries will be updated for internal use and further analysis and interpretation upon availability of new quality-checked data. Refined versions of the data summaries are publicly released in the Annual Report yearly.

Research Communication and Collaboration

A unique element of our university-based Monitoring Program is its ability to interface with other researchers, educators, and community scientists. At the 2023 Workshop more than 60 researchers, managers, and collaborators reported broadly on 2022 progress and identified key goals and questions for 2023. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Researchers attended and shared research at seven conferences and working groups in 2023, across ~ 10 posters and five presentations, listed in chronological order below under *Scientific Conferences and Working Groups*.

While some of the following efforts are outside the scope of the Program's core mandate and funding, the relationships built and scientific inquiry all feed back into strengthening the Program's understanding of restored wetlands. For example, the ability to expand hydrologic modeling and real-time collection of data by sensors are supported by the supplemental research listed below under *Leveraged Funds to Strengthen Monitoring Capacity*.

2023 Workshop

The 2023 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Annual Workshop (January 10th – 12th, 2023) brought together more than 60 researchers, managers, and collaborators to report broadly on 2022 progress and identify key goals and questions for 2023. Key takeaways include:

- 11 internal researchers and 7 invited complementary research “lightning talk” presentations (3 hours total, 18 slide decks).
- Internal researcher co-working sessions to refine surface water sampling strategy (1 draft program-wide conceptual model) and build upon nutrient budget frameworks (5 example project-specific conceptual models) and adapt broader program priorities as total projects increase (8 hours total).
- Small groups of ODNR project managers, WMP researchers, and conservation partners to exchange stories of successes and challenges and identify information needs unique to decisions faced in their respective roles (3 hours total, 30 completed guided worksheets).
- Informal networking among the wetland monitoring program’s various stakeholders to exchange feedback on wetland implementation, dialogue on details of restoration approaches, consider tradeoffs among different sampling schemes, and more (5 hours total, 8 completed guided worksheets).

Scientific Conferences and Working Groups

- Conference Poster: Myers J.A., Newell S.E., Grunden M., and S.J. Jacquemin S.J. of Wright State University presented the poster, “Assessing nutrient load reduction in a constructed wetland: A case study from Brooks Park” at the Ohio Academy of Science 2023 Meeting. (2023, April 15)
- Conference Presentation: Doro, K. Electrical Signals as Proxies for Wetland Soils Characteristics and Hydro-Biogeochemical Processes. [Oral Presentation]. Geological Society of America North-Central Meeting 2023 Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA. (2023, May 4-5) <https://rock.geosociety.org/net/documents/gsa/section/nc/2023/program.pdf>
- Conference Poster: LaPoint, H., & Doro, K. Rapid Site Characterization of Ohio Restored Wetlands Using Geophysics. Geological Society of America North-Central Meeting 2023 Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA. (2023, May 4-5) <https://gsa.confex.com/gsa/2023NC/meetingapp.cgi/Paper/386855>
- Conference Presentation: Otchere, N., & Doro, K. Combined Geophysics and Double-Ring Infiltration Tests Estimate Spatial Distribution of Infiltration Rates in Wetland Soils. [Oral Presentation]. Geological Society of America North-Central Meeting 2023 Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA. (2023, May 4-5). <https://rock.geosociety.org/net/documents/gsa/section/nc/2023/program.pdf>
- Conference Presentation: Urom, O., & Doro, K. Time-Lapse Monitoring of Varying Soil Water Saturation After Precipitation Using Electromagnetic Imaging. [Oral Presentation]. Geological Society of America North-Central Meeting 2023 Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA. (2023, May 4-5). <https://rock.geosociety.org/net/documents/gsa/section/nc/2023/program.pdf>

- Working Group Presentation: Lauren Kinsman-Costello (PI, Research Lead) gave a presentation to NOAA Gulf of Mexico and Central Region Collaboration Teams Nutrient Runoff Working Group. (2023, May 9)
- Conference Presentation: Olivia Johnson (Research Coordinator) attended the International Association of Great Lakes Research annual meeting and presented on the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program in the “Agricultural Best Management Practices” section. (2023, May 8-12).
- Conference Poster: Back, M., Watson, G., Horton, E., and Kinsman-Costello, L. Sediment-surface water nutrient flux in vegetation patches of a managed freshwater coastal wetland. Society of Freshwater Sciences 2023 Annual Meeting, Brisbane, Australia, (2023 June 5-9).
- Conference Poster: Kinsman-Costello, L.E., J. Kerns, O. Johnson, R. Mendonca, G. Liu, K. McCluney, H. Michaels, W.R. Midden, L.T. Johnson, J. Chaffin, R. Becker, T. Bridgeman, K. Doro, S. Newell, and S. Jacquemin. Evaluating nutrient function across diverse wetland restoration, construction, and enhancement projects: The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, Ohio, USA. Society of Freshwater Sciences 2023 Annual Meeting, Brisbane, Australia, (2023 June 5-9).
- Conference Poster: Mohammed, I., G. Liu, S. Lee, W.R. Midden, and L. Kinsman-Costello. Simulating hydrologic complexities of a nutrient-reduction wetland in the Midwest of the United States. The Geological Society of America Connects 2023 Annual Meeting, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, (2023, October 15-18).
- Conference Poster: Baumhower, B., G. Liu, S. Lee, P. Gorsevski, K. Otiso, and W.R. Midden. Suitability analysis for wetland restoration in the Blanchard River watershed in the Great Lakes region. The Geological Society of America Connects 2023 Annual Meeting, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, (2023, October 15-18).
- Conference Poster: Hoehn, Haley; L. Johnson, J. Boehler, and K. Peterson. Quantifying Primary Algal Groups in H2Ohio Wetlands. 52nd Annual Water Management Association of Ohio Meeting, Columbus, OH. (2023, November 7)
- Conference Poster: Peterson, Kelly; L. Johnson, and H. Hoehn. What Mud Can Do For You: Soil Removal of Phosphorus from H2Ohio Wetlands. 52nd Annual Water Management Association of Ohio Meeting. Columbus, OH. (2023, November 7).
- Conference Posters: H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Researchers participated in the Lake Erie and Aquatic Network First Annual Meeting at Heidelberg University. Silvia Newell (Michigan Sea Grant), Laura Johnson (Heidelberg), and Olivia Schloegel (Kent State) were on the meeting planning committee. Multiple undergraduate and graduate research posters featuring H2Ohio Wetland Projects were included at the event. (2023, November 9).

Leveraged Funds to Strengthen Monitoring Capacity

Supplemental Funding

- Ganming Liu (Bowling Green State University) received an Ohio Department of Higher Education Grant to expand 3-D hydrodynamic modeling at H2Ohio wetlands. (Contact: gliu@bgsu.edu)
- Janice Kerns (Ohio Department of Natural Resources), Lauren Kinsman-Costello (Kent State University) and Thomas Bridgeman (University of Toledo) received an US EPA

Great Lakes Restoration Initiative Grant to enhance sensor network implementation and calibration at H2Ohio wetlands. (Contact: janice.kerns@dnr.ohio.gov)

Public Communication and Outreach

2023 Webinar and Brochure

A public webinar was delivered on December 5, 2023, with 109 live viewers and 30 questions pre-submitted.; a 3-page case study of the Burntwood-Langenkamp project site accompanied the webinar. There have been 173 online views since the live presentation as of January 31, 2024.

Public Presentations and Outreach Events

- Public Presentation: Lauren Kinsman-Costello (PI, Research Lead) talked at OSU Extension Water Quality Team's Water Quality Wednesday to provide a "Wetlands and H2Ohio Update." Over 70 people attended; recording is available: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M_ZWqQKDUtc (2023, March 29)
- Outreach Event: Bob Midden and Genna Hunt (Bowling Green) hosted a visit at the Fox-Shank Living Lab Wetlands Project across from Otsego Schools for Nathan Hensley's Environmental Science class. They toured part of the site to explain the nature of the project to them, demonstrated the collection of water and soil samples and recording physicochemical parameters, and had the students collect some samples. (2023, October 17).